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Press Release

COVID-X programme's results are now available

The consortium of **COVID-X** announces the results of the **2-year initiative** that fast-tracked to market **28 European data technology solutions** to defeat COVID-19 Challenges, facilitating an innovative stack of AI-driven tools.

COVID-X has funded **EU Companies** and **Healthcare Providers** to boost data-driven solutions with the power to overcome challenges in Diagnosis, Prognosis, and Follow-up. The funding has been invested in products with TRL 7+, with or in the process of getting CE marking. COVID-X supported two profiles: **single solutions driven by** EU Tech SMEs / Start-Ups validating their products at one of the COVID-X clinical partners; and **team solutions** led by Tech companies working with a Healthcare provider to validate the product.

The selected projects joined an **acceleration program to boost their quick market uptake**, including technical support, ethical validation, and business coaching.

The COVID-X project has also delivered other valuable results. A technical infrastructure including a [unified data model](#), [sandbox and services](#) supports the processes of discovering and accessing data in a unified and seamless way, federated learning and training across different nodes of the distributed data infrastructure.

[Policy recommendations](#) help innovators navigate the landscape of launching a product to market and policymakers who can aid in solving the bottlenecks. Still, the healthcare institutions will find the recommendations helpful, making them more aware of the challenges the innovators face and working on breaking down the barriers from their side.

A [data anonymisation guide](#) describes the vital technical, organisational, and regulatory aspects of data anonymisation. This guide presents the procedure successfully tested for COVID-X that could easily be replicated in other clinical institutions.

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COVID-X involves a consortium of 10 partners from 7 different countries:

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